

Appendix A

Table 1 shows the hyperparameters used for each algorithm.

Table 1: Hyperparameters

Algorithms	Hyperparameters
BNB	alpha: 0.01, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 10.0; fit prior: True, False
LG	C: 0.01, 0.1, 1, 2, 10, 100; penalty: l2; multi class: multinomial solver: newtoncg, lbfgs; class weight*: balanced
SVM	C: 0.001, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 10.0 gamma: 0.001, 0.01, 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1.0, 10.0 kernel: rbf, poly, linear; probability: True
MLP	batch size: 8, 16 and 32; epochs: 10, 20, 40, 50 and 60 learning rate:0.0001, 0.0005, 0.001, 0.005, 0.01 class weight*: 0:0.65, 1:2.22

*This parameter was only used for the ReSpa dataset to address its imbalance issue.

Appendix B

Figure 1 represents the confusion matrices for the ensemble models using all the base models on Translated PROMISE_exp, and Figure 2 for the ensemble models using all the base models on ReSpa (the independent analysis on both cases).

Figure 1: Confusion matrix - Translated PROMISE_exp and all base models (a) Voting models, (b) Stacking BNB, (c) Stacking LR, (d) Stacking SVM, (e) Stacking MLP

Figure 2: Confusion matrix - ReSpa and all base models (a) Voting models, (b) Stacking BNB, (c) Stacking LR, (d) Stacking SVM, (e) Stacking MLP